

Research

Assessment of the Status of Urban Air Pollution and its Impact on Human Health in the City of Chittagong

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Abstract: Air pollution has significant effects on exacerbation of asthma, allergy and other respiratory diseases. There is a great need to implement control measures in most of the megacities of the world to improve air quality and hence protect public health. Like many other megacities in the world the ambient air quality of Chittagong is also being deteriorated day by day. Main sources of air pollution in this city are arising out of the emission from the motor-vehicles, industries, galvanisms, etc. Considering the severity of the problem, the current study plan was undertaken to measure the gaseous pollutants level in the air of different urban locations of Chittagong, the second largest city of Bangladesh. Atmospheric pollutants like gaseous (SO_2 , NO_2), particulate matters (SPM) were determined in Chittagong city. Eight different sampling stations, Muradpur Circle, WASA Circle, G.E.C Circle, Proborthak Circle, Chawk-bazaar Circle, Olongkar Circle, New Market Circle and Oxygen Circle were selected for sample collection and observations during the atmospheric year 2013 -2014. The objective of the study was to determine the concentrations of gaseous pollutants (SO_x , NO_x) and particulate matters (SPM, $PM_{2.5}$ and PM_{10}) to find out the variation of air pollutants in different locations of Chittagong city. The concentration of gaseous pollutants was found more at highly traffic areas. The highest concentration value of SO_2 , NO_2 and SPM was observed in highly traffic area at Muradpur Circle, Olongkar Circle & New Market Circle, respectively. The lowest concentration value was found in less traffic area at WASA Circle & Proborthak Circle. The average results of gaseous pollutants, particulate matters and trace metals have been compared to national and international standards. The value of SPM in air of Chittagong city is higher than that of TLV value recommended by WHO and DOE. The elemental concentrations (e.g. Cd, Co, Cr, Cu, Fe, Pb, Hg, Ni and Zn) of ambient air that collected at different locations in Chittagong city is exceeded the TLV. A strategic air quality management plan has been proposed.

Keywords: Chittagong City; Air Pollution; Health Impact; Particulate Matter; Gaseous Pollutants; Trace Metals.

Introduction

Air is a life sustaining precious natural resource. Fresh air is one of the most indispensable gifts of nature without which mankind cannot survive. But this air becomes polluted by various natural and anthropogenic activities (Rahman et al., 2000). Thousands of generations ago, humanity's mastery of fire led to biomass combustion that not only contaminated local living environments with smoke but also had a significant role in the global cycling of atmospheric constituents, particularly carbon (Smith 1993)

The important meteorological parameters that influence air pollution can be classified into primary parameters and secondary parameters (Rao and Rao, 1989). Air pollutant can be removed from the atmosphere by precipitation, different physical and chemical reactions, and also due to the gravitational forces (Perkins 1974). Particles in the size range 0.1-1.0 micrometer (μm) have the greatest influence on the absorption and scattering of solar radiation in the atmosphere. Therefore concentrations of these particles in the atmosphere are of special important to the planetary heat budget (Singer and Dordrecht, 1968). However, recently pollutants in micro-environments (vehicle inside, footpath, corridors etc.) are very much different from that in local monitoring stations (Karim et al., 1996). Automotive lead emissions have declined sharply in most OECD (Organization for Economic Development and Cooperation) countries whereas in developing countries they are rising. The contribution of developing countries to lead emission already exceeds that of OECD countries and measures are urgently needed to reduce or eliminate lead in the gasoline marketed in developing countries (Faiz, 1993). In the former USSR, the relatively higher share of CO emissions from the transport sector is attributable to the large proportion of gasoline-powered trucks and buses with very high emission rates (Makela, 1991). The higher share of SO_x emissions from automobiles in Bangladesh is due to the poor fuel quality and the extensive use of diesel-powered in some cases impure diesel vehicles. The share of motor vehicles in domestic emissions of fossil fuel CO₂ would be higher in Nigeria but lower in Bangladesh as a function of the percentage of petroleum fuel used in transport 59% in the United States, versus 74% in Nigeria and 28% in Bangladesh (Tylor, 1991). A study on emission source inventory performed in winter 1995 at Dhaka and found estimated total emissions for SO₂ and NO₂ to values 70 and 72 ton/day, respectively (Azad and Kitada, 1996). Increasing levels of carbon dioxide in the atmosphere may be responsible for long-term changes in Earth's climate. Those changes may have both beneficial and harmful effects on human and other forms of life on the planet (<http://www.scienceclarified.com/Ca-Ch/Carbon-Dioxide.html>). Carbon monoxide usually remains in the atmosphere for a month or two. It is removed by oxidation to form carbon dioxide, absorption by some plants and microorganisms and rain (De, 2010). Deaths have resulted from the inhalation of NO₂-containing gases from burning celluloid and nitrocellulose film and from spillage of NO₂ oxidant from missile rocket motors (Mashi et al., 2005). An increase of nitrous oxide concentration in atmosphere may also lead to a decrease in the stratospheric ozone concentration which may also affect surface temperature (Ming,

2004). Particle pollution exposure to a variety of problem including- increased respiratory symptoms such as irritation of the airways, coughing or difficult breathing, decrease lung function, aggravated asthma, development of chronic bronchitis, irregular heartbeat, non-fatal heart attacks, premature death in people with heart and lung disease, people with heart and lung disease, children and older adults are the most likely to be attacked by particle pollution exposure (Brunkreef and Holgate, 2002). It has been estimated that exposure to fine particulate matter in outdoor air leads to about 100 000 deaths (and 725 000 years of life lost) annually in Europe (WHO, 2003). In addition, if the particle consists of a mixture of purely scattering material such as ammonium sulfate and partially absorbing material such as soot, the cooling versus heating effect depends on the manner in which two substances are mixed throughout the particle pollution (Kiehl and Briegleb, 1993), (Kiehl, 1994). Accumulation in air is one major way through which heavy metals may find their way into soils and subsequently living tissues of plants, animals and human beings (Mashi et al., 2005). Moreover Iron, Nickel, Chromium, Antimony and Zinc, which are important additives in the manufacture of components of motor vehicle parts, are also emitted as a result of wear and tear (Adekola et al., 2002). In big cities, air is generally composed of car exhaust gas originated particles and wind-transported particles (Sezgin et al., 2004). The metals (e.g. Ni, Cr, Fe, Co, Mn, As, Pb, Zn, Cu, Mo, Cd) come mainly from vehicular activities such as wearing of tire (Zn, Pb, Cr and Ni) and wear of brake linings (Ni, Cr and Pb), corrosion of bushings, brake wires, radiators and the various types of de-icing chemicals and friction materials used on road surfaces for slipperiness control especially in temperate countries (Muschack, 1990), (Viklander, 1998). These elements eventually settle down on soil surfaces. In fact it has been shown that considerable amounts of toxic metals arising from human activities are accumulated in air (Agirtas and Kilicel, 1999). With rains, they are percolated into the soil and are eventually transferred into plants and eventually human through the consumption of this plants (Ahmed et al., 2012). They thus enter the food chain as a result of their uptake by edible plants (Kilice, 1999). Two stroke engine three wheeler vehicles have already been withdrawn from the city roads to protect the urban environment. These three wheeler vehicles were responsible for majority (around 60%) of the air pollution in the city. In fact, these three wheelers were popular vehicles among the middle class and upper middle class people of Chittagong city. By this time, Government of Bangladesh has imposed a ban on this 2 (two) stroke three wheelers and invited new 4 (four) stroke engine three wheeler compressed natural gas (CNG) vehicles to replace Two stroke vehicles. As a result of which, the city and the urban dwellers got rid of around 60% of air pollution by this time (Hashemi, 2006).

Materials and Methods

Selection of Sampling Locations

Chittagong City is not only the principal city of the district of Chittagong but also the second largest city of Bangladesh. It is situated within $22^{\circ} -14'$ and $22^{\circ} -24' -30'$ N Latitude and between $91^{\circ} -46'$ and $91^{\circ} -53'$ E Longitude and on the Right Bank of the river Karnafuli. 15 Eight important sampling locations in Chittagong city had been chosen for the collection of the air sample. These are Chawkbazar Circle, Proborthak Circle, Chittagong WASA Circle, Muradpur Circle, Olongkar Circle, G.E.C Circle, New Market Circle and Oxygen Circle.

Figure 1. Map of Bangladesh showing the location of Chittagong. Insert shows locations of Sampling Spot.

Sample Collection and Preparation

The sampling operation was carried out from morning to evening for eight hours. Weather condition was sunny in all sampling locations. A high volume sampler equipped with an impinger was used for the collection of NO₂ samples. The impinger contained 20 mL sodium Solution as absorbing solution. This absorbing solution was prepared before taking into the impinger. When the high volume sampler was on, this absorbing reagent started to absorb the NO₂ samples. After completing the eight hours sampling, the solution was taken to the laboratory for the measurement of the concentration of NO₂ in air. The amount of Nitrogen dioxide was then estimated by the color produced when hydrogen peroxide, sulfanilamide and NEDA solution were added by spectrophotometrically. The sampling time was varied from a few minutes to 24 hours. For 24 hours sampling, absorber is capable of holding 20-mL or more of absorbing reagent. A high volume sampler equipped with an impinger was used for the collection of SO₂ samples. The impinger contained 20-mL tetra-chloromercurate solution as absorbing solution. This absorbing solution was prepared before taking into the impinger. When the high volume sampler was on, this absorbing reagent started to absorb the SO₂ samples. After completing the eight hours sampling, the solution was taken to the laboratory for the measurement of the concentration of SO₂ in air. The absorbing reagent containing SO₂ formed a stable dichlorosulfitomercurate solution. The amount of sulfur dioxide was then estimated by the color produced when pararosaniline hydrochloride was added to the solution. Sampling impinger for the respective gases was used for sampling the atmospheric gaseous contents. High Volume Air Sampler in the selected areas from morning to evening (8 hours) was placed for the purpose. Respirable dust sampler was used for the collection of atmospheric particulate matters. UV/VIS-spectrophotometric technique was adopted for the determination of SO_x and NO_x content.

Procedure for Determination of SO₂

The general procedure for the determination of nitrogen dioxide has been shown in the following. In the blank preparation, 10-mL of unexposed tetrachloromercurate solution was taken in a volumetric flask, 1.0-mL of p-rosaniline and 1.0-mL of formaldehyde solution was added into it. If the collecting reagents remain exposed to the atmosphere during the interval between sampling and analysis, the blank will be exposed in the same manner. For the analysis of sulfur dioxide 10-mL of exposed tetrachloromercurate solution (sample) was taken in a volumetric flask, 1.0-mL of p-rosaniline and 1.00mL of formaldehyde solution was added into it. Mixed thoroughly after the addition of each reagent. It was allowed to stand for 10 minutes for the development of color in the solution. After 30 minutes, when the color developed fully in the solution, absorbance was measured at 560 nm against a corresponding reagent blank by using spectrophotometer. The sulfur dioxide content in an unknown sample was determined by using a concurrently prepared calibration graph.

Calculation:

The calculation of the volume of air sampled is as follows:

$$\frac{F_1 + F_2}{2} \times T \times 10^{-6}$$

Where,

V_s = volume of air sampled, (m³)

F₁ = measured flow rate before sampling, (mLmin⁻¹)

F₂ = measured flow rate during sampling, (mLmin⁻¹), and

T = time of sampling, (min.)

Again the calculation of the concentration of sulfur dioxide as follows:

The microliters of sulfur dioxide in the sample by multiplying the absorbance by the slope of the calibration plot. Then the concentration of sulfur dioxide in air is:

$$\frac{\mu\text{L of SO}_2 \times 20}{V_s}$$

Procedure for Determination of NO₂

The general procedure for the determination of nitrogen dioxide has been shown in the following. In the blank preparation, 10 mL of unexposed sodium hydroxide solution was taken in a volumetric flask, added 1.0-mL of hydrogen peroxide, 10.00mL of sulfanilamide solution, and 1.40-mL NEDA solution were added for thorough mixing after the addition of each reagent. After 10 minutes color will be developed. If the collecting reagents remain exposed to the atmosphere during the interval between sampling and analysis, the blank should be exposed in the same manner. For the analysis of nitrogen dioxide 10-mL of exposed sodium hydroxide solution was taken in a volumetric flask, added 1.00-mL of hydrogen peroxide, 10.00mL of sulfanilamide solution, and 1.40-mL NEDA solution were added for thorough mixing after the addition of each reagent. It was allowed to stand for 10 minutes for the development of color in the solution. After 30 minutes, when the color developed fully in the solution, absorbance was measured at 540 nm against the blank reagent by using Spectrophotometer. From the calibration curve, the concentration of NO₂ in the absorbing reagent was measured. After that the amount of NO₂ was measured by using following calculation.

Calculation:

The calculation of the volume of air sampled is as follows:

$$\frac{F_1 + F_2}{2} \times T \times 10^{-6}$$

Where,

V_s = volume of air sampled, (m³)

F₁ = measured initial flow rate before sampling, (mLmin⁻¹)

F₂ = measured final flow rate during sampling, (mLmin⁻¹), and

T = time of sampling, (min.)

Again the calculation of the concentration of nitrogen dioxide as follows:

The micro liters of nitrogen dioxide in the sample by multiplying the absorbance by the slope of the calibration plot. Then the concentration of nitrogen dioxide in air is:

$$\frac{\mu\text{L of NO}_2 \text{ mL}^{-1} \times 20}{V_s \times 0.35}$$

Where,

20 = volume of absorbing reagent used in sampling (mL)

V_s = volume of air sampled (m³)

0.35 Overall average efficiency.

Procedure for the Determination of SPM

SPM sample was collected in a filter paper by using high volume sampler (Envirotech). A filter paper was set up in the upper portion of the high volume sampler. The high volume air sampler was used to pump the large volume air into the absorber. When high volume air sampler was on, it started to pump air samples and SPM are stored in the filter paper. Before setting the filter paper in the upper portion of the high volume sampler, the initial weight of filter paper was taken by analytical balance. After completing the sampling the final weight of filter paper was taken by using the same balance. The amount SPM was obtained from the difference of above two results. SPM was determined by the following calculation (Ahmed et al., 2012).

Calculation:

$$\text{SPM in } \mu\text{gm}^{-3} = \frac{(\text{FFW} - \text{IFW}) \times 10^6}{\frac{(\text{IMR} + \text{FMR})}{2}} \times (\text{FTR} - \text{ITR}) \times 60$$

Where,

IFW = Weight of initial filter paper.

FFW= Weight of final filter paper.

IMR = Initial manometer reading.

FMR= Final manometer reading.

ITR = Initial time reading.

FTR = Final time reading.

Procedure for the Determination of Trace Metals

The whole Whattmann glass micro fiber filter paper was divided into four small pieces and taken into a beaker. Concentrated HNO₃ (5-mL) and H₂SO₄ (10-mL) were added to it successively. Then it placed into hot plate for an hour. After that it was removed from the hot plate and kept for cooling. The full filter paper was digested by using this procedure. Therefore, for the complete digestion of one filter paper this procedure was carried out four times with very carefully. When the cooling operation was completed then 20-mL de-ionized water added to it and neutralized by NH₃. Then it was filtered to a 100-mL volumetric flask. The same procedure was followed for the remaining portions of that filter paper. After collection of the all four dissolution of the same filter paper to the 100-mL volumetric flask, it was about 80-mL. The volumetric flask was up to the mark with de-ionized water and preserves it for the later analysis with highly caution. All the metal concentrations were determined by AA240FS fast sequential atomic absorption spectrophotometer (VARIAN) and GTA120 graphite tube atomizer, AA240ZZeeman atomic absorption spectrophotometer.

Calibration Curves for Metal Determination

Preparation of calibration curve for cadmium determination

1000 mgL⁻¹ of stock standard cadmium solution was prepared. For the preparation of 5mgL⁻¹ intermediate cadmium standard, 2.5mL stock cadmium standard was taken in a 500mL volumetric flask and diluted up to the mark with de-ionized water containing 10mL_{HNO₃}. 0.5, 1, and 2mgL⁻¹ working standard was prepared from 5-mgL⁻¹ intermediate standard for carrying out the analysis. 5mL for 0.5, 10mL for 1, 15 for 1.5, 20-mL for 2, 25-mL for 2.5-mgL⁻¹ was taken from the 5-mgL⁻¹ intermediate standard solution in separate 50mL volumetric flask. 1mL_{HNO₃} acid was added to each dilute up to the mark with de-ionized water. Working standard solution was prepared daily.

Preparation of calibration curve for cobalt determination

1000-mgL⁻¹ of stock standard Co solution was prepared. For the preparation of 10-mgL⁻¹ intermediate Co standard, 5-mL stock Co standard was taken in a 500-mL volumetric flask and diluted up to the mark with de-ionized water containing 10mL_{HNO₃}. 0.5, 1, and 2-mgL⁻¹ working standard was prepared from 10-mgL⁻¹ intermediate standard for carrying out the analysis. 2.5-mL for 0.5, 5-mL for 1.00, and 10-mL for 2-mgL⁻¹ was taken from the 10-mgL⁻¹ intermediate standard solution in separate 50-mL volumetric flask. 1mL_{HNO₃} acid was added to each dilute up to the mark with de-ionized water. Working standard solution was prepared daily.

Preparation of calibration curve for chromium determination

1000-mgL⁻¹ of stock standard chromium solution was prepared. For the preparation of 5-mgL⁻¹ intermediate chromium standard, 2.5-mL stock chromium standard was taken in a 500mL volumetric flask and diluted up to the mark with de-ionized water containing 10mL_{HNO₃}. 0.2, 0.5, 1, and 2 mgL⁻¹ working standard was prepared from 5-mgL⁻¹ intermediate standard for carrying out the analysis. 2-mL for 0.2, 5mL for 0.5, 10mL for 1, 15 ml for 1.5 and 20-mL for 2-mgL⁻¹ was taken from the 5-mgL⁻¹ intermediate standard solution in separate 50-mL volumetric flask. 1-mL HNO₃ acid was added to each dilute up to the mark with de-ionized water. Working standard solution was prepared daily.

Preparation of calibration curve for copper determination

1000-mgL⁻¹ of stock standard Cu solution was prepared. For the preparation of 10-mgL⁻¹ intermediate Cu standard, 5-mL stock Cu standard was taken in a 500-mL volumetric flask and diluted up to the mark with de-ionized water containing 10mL_{HNO₃}. 0.5, 1, 2 and 4-mgL⁻¹ working standard was prepared from 10 mgL⁻¹ intermediate standard for carrying out the analysis. 2.5-mL for 0.5, 5-mL for 1.0, 10-mL for 2 and 20mL for 4mgL⁻¹ was taken from the 10 mgL⁻¹ intermediate standard solution in separate 50mL volumetric flask. 1mL_{HNO₃} acid was added to each dilute up to the mark with de-ionized water. Working standard solution was prepared daily.

Preparation of calibration curve for iron determination

1000-mgL⁻¹ of stock standard Fe solution was prepared. For the preparation of 10-mgL⁻¹ intermediate Fe standard, 5-mL stock Fe standard was taken in a 500-mL volumetric flask and diluted up to the mark with de-ionized water containing 10-mL_{HNO₃}. 0.5, 1, 2 and 4-mgL⁻¹

working standard was prepared from 10mgL⁻¹ intermediate standard for carrying out the analysis. 2.5-mL for 0.5, 5-mL for 1.00, 10-mL for 2 and 20-mL for 4-mgL⁻¹ was taken from the 10-mgL⁻¹ intermediate standard solution in separate 50-mL volumetric flask. 1-mL HNO₃ acid was added to each dilute up to the mark with de-ionized water. Working standard solution was prepared daily.

Preparation of calibration curve for lead determination

1000-mgL⁻¹ of stock standard Pb solution was prepared. For the preparation of 10-mgL⁻¹ intermediate Pb standard, 5-mL stock Pb standard was taken in a 500mL volumetric flask and diluted up to the mark with de-ionized water containing 10-mL HNO₃. 0.5, 1, 2 and 4-mgL⁻¹ working standard was prepared from 10-mgL⁻¹ intermediate standard for carrying out the analysis. 2.5-mL for 0.5, 5-mL for 1.00, 10-mL for 2, 15-mL for 3 and 20-mL for 4-mgL⁻¹ was taken from the 10-mgL⁻¹ intermediate standard solution in separate 50mL volumetric flask. 1-mL HNO₃ acid was added to each dilute up to the mark with de-ionized water. Working standard solution was prepared daily.

Preparation of calibration curve for mercury determination

1000-mgL⁻¹ of stock standard mercury solution was prepared. For the preparation of 5-mgL⁻¹ intermediate mercury standard, 2.5-mL stock mercury standard was taken in a 500-mL volumetric flask and diluted up to the mark with de-ionized water containing 10-mL HNO₃. 0.1, 0.2, 0.4 and 0.8-mgL⁻¹ working standard was prepared from 5-mgL⁻¹ intermediate standard for carrying out the analysis. 1-mL for 0.1, 2-mL for 0.2, 4-mL for 0.4, 6-mL for 0.6 and 8-mL for 0.8-mgL⁻¹ was taken from the 5-mgL⁻¹ intermediate standard solution in separate 50-mL volumetric flask. 1-mL HNO₃ acid was added to each dilute up to the mark with de-ionized water. Working standard solution was prepared daily.

Preparation of calibration curve for nickel determination

1000-mgL⁻¹ of stock standard Ni solution was prepared. For the preparation of 10-mgL⁻¹ intermediate Ni standard, 5-mL stock Ni standard was taken in a 500-mL volumetric flask and diluted up to the mark with de-ionized water containing 10-mL HNO₃. 0.5, 1, 2 and 4-mgL⁻¹ working standard was prepared from 10mgL⁻¹ intermediate standard for carrying out the analysis. 2.5-mL for 0.5, 5-mL for 1.00, 10-mL for 2 and 20-mL for 4-mgL⁻¹ was taken from the 10-mgL⁻¹ intermediate standard solution in separate 50mL volumetric flask. 1-mL HNO₃ acid was added to each dilute up to the mark with de-ionized water. Working standard solution was prepared daily.

Preparation of calibration curve for zinc determination

1000-mgL⁻¹ of stock standard zinc solution was prepared. For the preparation of 5-mgL⁻¹ intermediate zinc standard, 2.5-mL stock zinc standard was taken in a 500-mL volumetric flask and diluted up to the mark with de-ionized water containing 10-mL HNO₃. 0.1, 0.2, 0.4 and 0.8-mgL⁻¹ working standard was prepared from 5-mgL⁻¹ intermediate standard for carrying out the analysis. 1-mL for 0.1, 2-mL for 0.2, 4-mL for 0.4, 6-mL for 0.6 and 8-mL for 0.8-mgL⁻¹ was taken from the 5-mgL⁻¹ intermediate standard solution in separate 50-mL volumetric flask. 1-mL HNO₃ acid was added to each dilute up to the mark with de-ionized water. Working standard solution was prepared daily.

Results and Discussion

The suspended Particulate matters were measured in different traffic locations in Chittagong city ambient air. The average concentration of suspended particulate matter was found $802.90-\mu\text{gm}^{-3}$ for all sampling locations in Chittagong city which was higher than the daily average given by WHO. The average concentration of SPM were found in Muradpur Circle, WASA Circle, G.E.C Circle, Proborthak Circle, Chawkbazar Circle, Olongkar Circle, New Market Circle and Oxygen Circle was $684.588-\mu\text{gm}^{-3}$, $654.487-\mu\text{gm}^{-3}$, $818.797-\mu\text{gm}^{-3}$, $673.113-\mu\text{gm}^{-3}$, $863.677-\mu\text{gm}^{-3}$, $890.613-\mu\text{gm}^{-3}$, $949.102-\mu\text{gm}^{-3}$, $888.849-\mu\text{gm}^{-3}$, respectively in air of Chittagong city. The highest concentration of SPM was found in highly traffic area New Market Circle. The SPM concentrations were varying from $949.101-\mu\text{gm}^{-3}$ New Market Circle to $654.486-\mu\text{gm}^{-3}$ WASA Circle. The concentration of SPM in all sampling station in Chittagong city is higher than the DOE value. The concentration of suspended particulate matter in Chittagong city air has shown in Table 1. The cause of higher value of SPM in Chittagong city air are incomplete combustion of fossil fuel of vehicles included car, jeep, bus, minibus, truck, human holler, microbus, four stroke engine driven vehicles like auto rickshaw, CNG etc and motorbikes. Railway engines, industrial plants, power plants, brick fields.

Table 1. The SPM concentration of different locations in Chittagong city.

Sampling Date	Location	Weather Condition	Sampling Hour	Concentration of SPM (μgm^{-3})
16.02.2014, Sunday		Sunny	8 hour	682.875
17.04.2014, Thursday	Muradpur Circle	Sunny	8 hour	695.106
16.05.2014, Friday		Sunny	8 hour	675.783
Average			684.588	
09.02.2014, Sunday		Sunny	8 hour	705.610
04.04.2014, Friday	WASA Circle	Sunny	8 hour	655.540
05.06.2014, Thursday		Sunny	8 hour	602.310
Average			654.487	
16.03.2014, Sunday		Sunny	8 hour	855.752
15.05.2014, Thursday	G.E.C Circle	Sunny	8 hour	825.64
08.08.2014, Friday		Sunny	8 hour	775
Average			818.797	
07.03.2014, Friday		Sunny	8 hour	662.678
10.07.2014, Thursday	Proborthak Circle	Sunny	8 hour	674.251
03.08.2014, Sunday		Sunny	8 hour	682.41
Average			673.113	
23.03.2014, Sunday		Sunny	8 hour	870.301
	Chawkbazar Circle			
20.06.2014, Friday		Sunny	8 hour	855.29
21.08.2014, Thursday		Sunny	8 hour	865.441
Average			863.677	
07.02.2014, Friday		Sunny	8 hour	878.716
06.04.2014, Sunday	Olongkar Circle	Sunny	8 hour	902.817
14.08.2014, Thursday		Sunny	8 hour	890.305
Average			890.613	
04.05.2014, Sunday		Sunny	8 hour	980.601
	New Market Circle			
03.07.2014, Thursday		Sunny	8 hour	950.501
01.08.2014, Friday		Sunny	8 hour	916.203
Average			949.102	
26.06.2014, Thursday		Sunny	8 hour	893.251
11.07.2014, Friday	Oxygen Circle	Sunny	8 hour	875.356
10.08.2014, Sunday		Sunny	8 hour	897.941
Average			888.849	

Open burning incineration, solid waste disposal sites, road side dust particles, road diggings, constructions and other development activities are also contributing to the higher value of suspended particulate matter in air of Chittagong city. The gaseous pollutants SO_2 and NO_2 were determined by using high volume sampler at the different locations such as Muradpur Circle, WASA Circle, G.E.C Circle, Proborthak Circle, Chawkbazar Circle, Olongkar Circle, New

Market Circle and Oxygen Circle in Chittagong city. The sampling was done at different locations in different months in air of Chittagong city. The average concentrations of SO₂ were found 37.20- μgm^{-3} , 26.25- μgm^{-3} , 36.32- μgm^{-3} , 31.41- μgm^{-3} , 33.19- μgm^{-3} , 35.48- μgm^{-3} , 30.51- μgm^{-3} and 35.63- μgm^{-3} in the above locations.

Table 2. The concentration of NO₂ and SO₂ of different locations in Chittagong city

Sampling Date	Location	Weather Condition	Sampling Hour	Concentration of NO ₂ (μgm^{-3})	Concentration of SO ₂ (μgm^{-3})
16.02.2014, Sunday		Sunny	8 hour	46.28	38.95
17.04.2014, Thursday	Muradpur Circle	Sunny	8 hour	45.17	37.21
16.05.2014, Friday		Sunny	8 hour	43.27	35.45
Average			44.91	37.20	
09.02.2014, Sunday		Sunny	8 hour	48.39	26.47
04.04.2014, Friday	WASA Circle	Sunny	8 hour	46.31	24.07
05.06.2014, Thursday		Sunny	8 hour	49.98	28.21
Average			48.23	26.25	
16.03.2014, Sunday		Sunny	8 hour	45.9	36.83
15.05.2014, Thursday	G.E.C Circle	Sunny	8 hour	45.28	36.21
08.08.2014, Friday		Sunny	8 hour	43.49	35.92
Average			44.89	36.32	
07.03.2014, Friday		Sunny	8 hour	37.17	30.06
10.07.2014, Thursday	Proborthak Circle	Sunny	8 hour	39.29	32.01
03.08.2014, Sunday		Sunny	8 hour	39.61	32.17
Average			38.69	31.41	
23.03.2014, Sunday		Sunny	8 hour	42.91	33.41
20.06.2014, Friday	Chawkbazar Circle	Sunny	8 hour	41.72	32.55
21.08.2014, Thursday		Sunny	8 hour	43.08	33.6
Average			42.57	33.19	
07.02.2014, Friday		Sunny	8 hour	59.95	34.67
06.04.2014, Sunday	Olongkar Circle	Sunny	8 hour	61.05	35.81
14.08.2014, Thursday		Sunny	8 hour	61.86	35.95
Average			60.95	35.48	
04.05.2014, Sunday		Sunny	8 hour	51.48	31.43
03.07.2014, Thursday	New Market Circle	Sunny	8 hour	50.62	30.21
01.08.2014, Friday		Sunny	8 hour	49.48	29.9
Average			50.527	30.51	
26.06.2014, Thursday		Sunny	8 hour	58.47	35.65
11.07.2014, Friday	Oxygen Circle	Sunny	8 hour	56.03	34.14
10.08.2014, Sunday		Sunny	8 hour	58.31	37.09
Average			57.603	35.63	

In these sampling maximum concentrations $37.20-\mu\text{gm}^{-3}$ was found at Muradpur Circle is shown in Table 2. The main reason for this maximum value was heavy traffic spot, open oven of restaurant and vehicular emissions. The lowest value was found $26.15-\mu\text{gm}^{-3}$ at WASA Circle because less traffic area, less industrial and vehicular emissions. The reason for the higher concentration of SO_x in air is because of the higher sulfur content in our imported oil. The

average concentrations of NO₂ were found 44.90- μgm^{-3} , 48.23- μgm^{-3} , 44.89- μgm^{-3} , 38.69- μgm^{-3} , 42.57- μgm^{-3} , 60.95- μgm^{-3} , 50.52- μgm^{-3} , and 57.60- μgm^{-3} in the respective different locations in air of Chittagong city. In these average values the maximum value 60.95- μgm^{-3} was found at Olongkar Circle. The lowest value was 38.69- μgm^{-3} found at Proborthak Circle. The concentration of the gaseous pollutants NO₂ at different locations in Chittagong city has been shown in the Table 2. In both cases the concentration of SO₂ and NO₂ were found to be lower with comparing the annual standard value of DOE, Bangladesh and WHO Guideline values in 8 hours average time.

The average concentration of trace metals were 7.845- μgm^{-3} , less than 0.01- μgm^{-3} , 9.637- μgm^{-3} , 0.381- μgm^{-3} , 0.169- μgm^{-3} , 0.38- μgm^{-3} , less than 0.01- μgm^{-3} , 0.052- μgm^{-3} and 22.594- μgm^{-3} for Cd, Co, Cr, Cu, Fe, Pb, Hg, Ni and Zn, respectively at Muradpur Circle.

Table 3. The trace metal (Cd, Co, Cr, Cu, Fe, Pb, Hg, Ni and Zn) concentrations of different locations in Chittagong city.

Sampling Date	Location	Cd	Co	Cr	Cu	Fe	Pb	Hg	Ni	Zn
Units in μgm^{-3}										
16.02.2014, Sunday	Muradpur Circle	8.13		9.68	0.3	0.1	0.6		0.0	24.1
		8.21	^a B		91	82	5		58	12
17.04.2014, Thursday	Muradpur Circle	11	DL	9.58	0.3	0.1	0.4	^a B	0.0	22.9
16.05.2014, Friday		7.19			85	56	5	DL	51	82
Average	Muradpur Circle	7.84		9.63	0.3	0.1	0.3		0.0	22.5
		5		7	81	69	8		52	94
09.02.2014, Sunday	WASA Circle	16.1		53.8	0.5	6.9	9.6	0.7	0.5	66.7
		2		4	81	7	3	8	66	81
04.04.2014, Friday	WASA Circle	16.0	BD	53.6	0.5	6.6	9.2	0.6	0.4	66.5
		2	L	2	23	6	8	4	96	95
05.06.2014, Thursday	WASA Circle	16.1		53.9	0.5	6.8	9.4	0.7	0.5	66.8
		8		1	73	2	1	1	71	85
Average	WASA Circle	16.1		53.7	0.5	6.8	9.4	0.7	0.5	66.7
		07		9	59	17	4	1	44	54
16.03.2014, Sunday	G.E.C Circle	12.1			0.2		0.2	0.1	0.2	17.4
		6		3.85	47		5	6	51	03
15.05.2014, Thursday	G.E.C Circle	11.7	BD		0.1	BD	0.2	0.1	0.2	14.1
		8	L	3.91	89	L	2	2	01	58
08.08.2014, Friday	G.E.C Circle	11.2			0.1		0.1	0.0	0.1	12.4
		9		3.76	56		6	9	96	73
Average	G.E.C Circle	11.7		3.84	0.1		0.2	0.1	0.2	14.6
		43		3.84	97		1	23	16	8
07.03.2014, Friday	Proborthak Circle	5.98		6.17	0.2	0.2	0.0		0.0	11.9
					83	98	7		28	79
10.07.2014, Thursday	Proborthak Circle		BD		0.3	0.3	0.0	BD	0.0	13.0
		6.02	L	6.31	14	06	9	L	34	21
03.08.2014, Sunday	Proborthak Circle				0.2	0.3	0.1		0.0	13.1
		6.16		6.23	98	51	3		39	53
Average	Proborthak Circle	6.05		6.23	0.2	0.3	0.0		0.0	12.7
		3		7	98	18	97		34	18
23.03.2014, Sunday		14.2		38.9	0.3		8.0		0.4	31.0

		43		1	61		3		8	11
20.06.2014, Friday	Chawkbazar Circle	14.5 94	BD L	38.6 3	0.2 59	BD L	7.7 9	BD L	0.3 4	29.2 26
		15.2		36.4	0.3		7.9		0.5	29.9
21.08.2014 Thursday		06		1	42		3		3	81
	Average	14.6		37.9	0.3		7.9		0.4	30.0
		81		83	2		17		5	73
07.02.2014, Friday		5.8		0.97	08		5		96	5
	Olongkar Circle		BD		0.3	BD	0.0	BD	0.1	5.90
06.04.2014, Sunday		6.3	L	1.61	61	L	8	L	92	7
					0.3		0.1		0.1	6.09
14.08.2014, Thursday		8.13		1.93	93		6		78	1
	Average	6.74		1.50	0.2		0.0		0.1	5.87
		3		3	87		97		55	4
		11.1		16.1	0.5	0.8	6.1		0.1	21.8
04.05.2014, Sunday		8		7	11	16	7		41	3
03.07.2014, Thursday	New Market Circle		BD	18.0	0.5	0.9	6.0	BD	0.1	24.2
01.08.2014, Friday		9.56	L	9	11	01	1	L	73	5
				17.5	0.5	0.9	6.2		0.1	23.5
		9.47		1	43	12	1		54	2
	Average	10.0		17.2	0.5	0.8	6.1		0.1	23.2
		7		6	22	76	3		56	0
		12.4		31.0	0.2	0.7	9.8		0.6	20.5
26.06.2014, Thursday		6		8	16	81	3		35	76
11.07.2014, Friday	Oxygen Circle	12.5 9	BD L	29.5 6	0.2 51	0.7 49	8.6 1	BD L	0.5 91	21.3 61
		12.0		35.9	0.2	0.7	8.7		0.3	25.2
10.08.2014, Sunday		6		3	1	93	4		29	41
	Average	12.3		32.1	0.2	0.7	9.0		0.5	22.3
		7		9	26	74	6		18	9

^aBDL = Below the Detection Limit
(Less than 0.01- μgm^{-3})

The average concentration of trace metals were 16.107- μgm^{-3} , less than 0.01- μgm^{-3} , 53.79- μgm^{-3} , 0.559- μgm^{-3} , 6.817- μgm^{-3} , 9.44- μgm^{-3} , 0.71- μgm^{-3} , 0.544- μgm^{-3} , and 66.754- μgm^{-3} for Cd, Co, Cr, Cu, Fe, Pb, Hg, Ni and Zn, respectively at WASA Circle. The average concentration of trace metals were 11.743- μgm^{-3} , less than 0.01- μgm^{-3} , 3.84- μgm^{-3} , 0.197- μgm^{-3} , less than 0.01- μgm^{-3} , 0.21- μgm^{-3} , 0.123- μgm^{-3} , 0.216- μgm^{-3} and 14.68 μgm^{-3} for Cd, Co, Cr, Cu, Fe, Pb, Hg, Ni and Zn, respectively at G.E.C Circle. The average concentration of trace metals were 6.053- μgm^{-3} , less than 0.01- μgm^{-3} , 6.237- μgm^{-3} , 0.298- μgm^{-3} , 0.318- μgm^{-3} , 0.097- μgm^{-3} , less than 0.01- μgm^{-3} , 0.034- μgm^{-3} and 12.718- μgm^{-3} for Cd, Co, Cr, Cu, Fe, Pb, Hg, Ni and Zn, respectively at Proborthak Circle. The average concentration of trace metals were 14.681- μgm^{-3} , less than 0.01- μgm^{-3} , 37.983- μgm^{-3} , 0.32- μgm^{-3} , less than 0.01- μgm^{-3} , 7.917- μgm^{-3} , less than 0.01- μgm^{-3} , 0.45- μgm^{-3} and 30.073- μgm^{-3} for Cd, Co, Cr, Cu, Fe, Pb, Hg, Ni and Zn, respectively at Chawkbazar Circle. The average concentration of trace metals were 6.743- μgm^{-3} , less than 0.01- μgm^{-3} , 1.503- μgm^{-3} , 0.287- μgm^{-3} , less than 0.01- μgm^{-3} , 0.097- μgm^{-3} , less than 0.01- μgm^{-3} , 0.155- μgm^{-3} and 5.874- μgm^{-3} for Cd, Co, Cr, Cu, Fe, Pb, Hg, Ni and Zn, respectively at Olongkar Circle. The average concentration of trace metals were 10.07- μgm^{-3} , less than 0.01- μgm^{-3} , 17.26- μgm^{-3} , 0.522- μgm^{-3} , 0.876- μgm^{-3}

$\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$, $6.13\text{-}\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$, less than $0.01\text{-}\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$, $0.156\text{-}\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$, $23.20\text{-}\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ for Cd, Co, Cr, Cu, Fe, Pb, Hg, Ni and Zn, respectively at New Market Circle. The average concentration of trace metals were $12.37\text{-}\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$, less than $0.01\text{-}\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$, $32.19\text{-}\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$, $0.226\text{-}\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$, $0.774\text{-}\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$, $9.06\text{-}\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$, less than $0.01\text{-}\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$, $0.518\text{-}\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$, $22.39\text{-}\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ for Cd, Co, Cr, Cu, Fe, Pb, Hg, Ni and Zn, respectively at Oxygen Circle. The zinc concentration of current study was found very high in comparison with other results. This is due to the high welding industries in Chittagong City which is shown in Table 3.

Conclusions

Everyone contributes to national and global emissions of pollutant gases, but it is not only governments that can take action to reduce the environmental damage caused. For their policies to work effectively and for their targets to be achieved the actions of the individual are required. The cumulative energy reductions by individuals would reduce the need for energy consumption, conserve stocks of raw materials such as coal, oil and gas, and bring about a reduction in pollutant gas emissions. In general, there is only a limited understanding of air quality in Chittagong. The rapid urban development that has occurred and is ongoing in Dhaka is also occurring in Chittagong and therefore Government has recognized that there is a real need to improve air quality management capacity in Chittagong. At present air pollution due to anthropogenic activities is confirmed. In order to understand the possible effects in medicine, biology, ecology and climatology; the sources, transport mechanism and sinks of air pollution need to be known in some details.

Table 4. Comparison of trace metal concentration of current study with other cities data.

City	Location	Cu	Mn	Pb	Cd	
		Units in $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$				References
Beijing, China		-	1.21	0.046	0.075	Mori et al., 2003
Islamabad, Pakistan		-	0.059	0.214	0.015	Shaheen et al., 2005
Vienna, Austria		0.0031	0.0024	0.017	0.00044	Puxbaun et al., 2004
		0.0017	0.002	0.012	0.00023	
Teheran, Iran		-	0.078	1.02	1.120	Rostami et al., 1999
Bangladesh	Bahaddarhat	3.95	0.696	0.42	0.018	
(Chittagong City)	Newmarket	2.2	0.951	0.745	0.0245	
	Nasirabad	4.99	1.1	0.3	0.017	Ahmed et al., 2012
	G.E.C Circle	14.48	0.54	0.16	0.0165	
	Director's Office	12.69	0.74	0.55	0.021	

Current Study Location	Cd	Co	Cr	Cu	Fe	Pb	Hg	Ni	Zn

	Units in μgm^{-3}								
Muradpur Circle	7.845	^a BDL	9.637	0.381	0.169	0.38	^a BDL	0.052	22.594
WASA Circle	16.107	^a BDL	53.79	0.559	6.817	9.44	0.71	0.544	66.754
G.E.C Circle	11.743	^a BDL	3.84	0.197	^a BDL	0.21	0.123	0.216	14.68
Proborthak Circle	6.053	^a BDL	6.237	0.298	0.318	0.097	^a BDL	0.034	12.718
Chawkbazar Circle	14.681	^a BDL	37.983	0.32	^a BDL	7.917	^a BDL	0.45	30.073
Olongkar Circle	6.743	^a BDL	1.503	0.287	^a BDL	0.097	^a BDL	0.155	5.874
New Market Circle	10.07	^a BDL	17.26	0.522	0.876	6.13	^a BDL	0.156	23.2
Oxygen Circle	12.37	^a BDL	32.19	0.226	0.774	9.06	^a BDL	0.518	22.39

^aBDL = Less than $0.01 \mu\text{gm}^{-3}$

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Dedication

Not mentioned.

Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

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